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Conflicting Conceptualisations of Europeanisation

Hungary Country Report

Umut Korkut

Glasgow Caledonian University

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Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to us at umut.korkut@gcu.ac.uk

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About the project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project that aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the European Union (EU), its Member States and third countries.

RESPOND will study migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanisation. Each thematic field reflects a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and is designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impact and the responses given by affected actors.

In order to better approach these themes, we divided our research into work packages (WPs). The present report is concerned with the findings related to WP5, which focuses specifically on refugee integration.

Executive Summary

This report reviews the unfolding of the future of Europe and external migration related narratives in Hungary, and the liberal/conservative dilemmas that Hungarian politicians proposed since 2015. Its particular scope is the Prime Minister Viktor Orbán's speeches and how they were quoted by or referred to in the Hungarian media. The abrupt increase in the number of irregular migrant arrivals to Hungary prepared the conditions for Orbán to project the course that he foresaw for the conservative transformation for Hungary to transform Europe. After his victory in 2010 and 2014 at Hungarian general elections, Orbán presented his country as the vanguard for the conservative transformation that Europe also needed. In this respect, external migration from those countries where Islam was the majority religion presented Orbán the context whereby he could project the historical other for Europe as the future danger. What followed his narrative was also a major transformation of the institutional and policy aspects of migration management in Hungary, which limited protection and reception to detention and removal. While in Orbán's discourse, circulated extensively by the Hungarian conservative, liberal, and centrist media, inasmuch as Europe was facing an imminent danger, it was Hungary and the course that it has followed in response to external migration, which was the answer. In order to summarise the evolution of this narrative, I can further list the following.

- Orbán presented external migration to Europe as a central threat to the pillars of EU integration. He has organised his alternative Europeanisation discourse based on the failure of "liberal" Europe, including the EU institutions, to respond to this asserted threat.
- Orbán's discourse and projections have not remained as indigenous solutions and not necessarily nativist. He has depicted Hungarian solutions to external migration also as an answer for European "migration problem"
- Orbán sought to present Hungary as the true European actor with its overt concern and care for Europe's future and the security of its citizens.
- Orbán proposed solutions based on national sovereignty to promote those policies that Hungary enacted as solutions. He maintains a criticism of other EU national elites but primarily focuses on the European Commission – or EU bureaucrats – whom he considers being at the root of the crisis that Europeanisation experiences facing the volume of irregular external migration.
- While the conservative media endorsed Orbán's discourse on the important role that the EU member nation states should play in response to external migration, the left-liberal media was clear with its message that in order to have a strong EU, the EU institutions should play pivotal roles in migration management.
- It is noteworthy that, regardless of ideological colour, all conservative, left-liberal and centrist media elaborated on the theme of "danger" that migrants and refugees posed to Europe.
- Amidst a muddled system of migration governance at the European level, Orbán consolidates his own conservative migration and Europeanisation narrative as an alternative to the liberal course of Europeanisation that held sway in the EU for decades. In a way, the new "Promoting the European way of Life" agenda and the EU Pact on migration and asylum give indications that Orbán's conservative agenda for the future course of Europeanisation has resonated extensively in Brussels.

Introduction

This report has two analytical aims. Its contextual analysis reflects on the structure of political parties and newspaper media in Hungary. Its empirical analysis shows the multifaceted make-up of Europeanisation in view of external migration, and its narrativization by Hungarian politicians with the aim of building audiences supportive of their aspirations for the future of Europe. Therefore, it examines how Hungarian politicians tied their domestic political goals with the course of Europeanisation, and reimagined the course of Europeanisation in terms of what they aim to achieve at home. In this regard, the abrupt increase in the number of irregular migrants arriving at in Hungary, starting with June 2015, presented Fidesz politicians with an opportunity to first reinterpret Europe as a continent under threat and second to put their sway on its future course of integration, defending the claim that the continent has to be protected from the “other”. To this extent, they have basically essentialised the “other” as Muslim migrants.

This report concentrates on Orbán’s narrative, given his eminence in Hungarian politics, and his political party Fidesz-MPP (Alliance of Young Democrats-Hungarian Civic Party) – widely known as Fidesz. The evolution of Fidesz from a liberal party in the 1990s into a conservative right-wing party, and the parallel transformation of its stance on Europeanisation, is noteworthy for our purposes. We underline this transformation not only for Hungarian, but also for European politics given the resonance that Viktor Orbán’s discourses on migration and the future of Europe has gained in the EU amidst and in the aftermath of the abrupt increase in the number of irregular migrant arrivals to Europe in 2015. The Italian report by Marchesi and Terlizzi (2020) for WP6 show how the Hungarian discourse resonated in Italy. Similarly, we come across the sovereignty arguments that Hungary and other Visegrad countries proposed against the quota regime endorsed in the WP6 German Report (Nagel 2020).

The Hungarian case also suggests that political parties pragmatically reinterpret Europeanisation to serve their political ends, and they would have ever-shifting positions across a spectrum from EU-reject to EU-philia depending on how they frame their country’s identity as an extension of Europe vis-à-vis either the European or the non-European other. The way Fidesz has instrumentalized its position towards European integration defies the existing definitions of Europhilia, Euroscepticism and Europragmatism (Szczzerbiak and Taggart eds. 2008 and Kopecký and Mudde 2002), and shows that a political party can sustain an EU-pragmatic image while simultaneously aggregating and juggling different ideological positions towards the conditions and processes of EU integration in promotion of their politics. As such the position that Fidesz has adopted towards external migration provided it with a chance to pragmatically present itself as truly European – the one who raises the alarm for EU’s future – and to criticise the EU from the standpoint of the one who decries first the failure of “liberal course of Europeanisation” that has involved liberal and open migration politics and second the European Commission as a party to this failure. The case of Fidesz also shows that the EU-pragmatists can be active-pragmatics rather than neutral-pragmatics with respect to European integration and hence look for ways to generate audiences for their proposed course of Europeanisation.

A study of their view on external migration presents a pertinent case study to explore how they seek alternative forms of Europeanisation that stand in opposition to a liberal migration regime led by supranational EU agencies. This report presents the Hungarian case to this extent and contextualises it to explore how a conservative course of Europeanisation would clash with a liberal course.

Methodology

This report is empirically focused first and foremost on Viktor Orbán's speeches regarding external migration and Europe. While the RESPOND project covers a period from 2011 to 2018, migration gained much relevance in Hungarian politics after the end of 2014, and reached its climax as a political issue starting with 2015. This is due to the increasing irregular arrivals of migrants to Hungary, first from the Western Balkans and later from the Middle East and beyond starting with mid-2015. While Viktor Orbán's slogans, tropes, narratives, and metaphors have become central to migration politics and policy in Hungary, opposition to his politics also quietened and became almost imperceptible.¹ Furthermore, in view of external migration and the future of Europeanisation, Viktor Orbán's voice has gained traction not only in Hungary but also in the rest of the European Union (see Marchesi and Terlizzi forthcoming and Nagel 2020). This is the reason why the analysis in this report is concentrated mostly on Orbán's speeches. However, I also present the narratives of other Fidesz ministers to represent the homogenous composition of the opposition in Hungary against external migration to Europe and Hungary. Below, I am introducing quotations from 25 speeches extracted from mostly Orbán's as well as other Fidesz politicians. The section on interpretations of external migration in Hungary below presents an overview of the most dominant themes in these speeches.

Second, this report looks at the conservative, centrist, and liberal media outlets in Hungary in order to see how they have embedded narratives, slogans and tropes from these speeches. The idea here is to trace the cultivation of diverse audiences with the same political message funnelled through the ideological focus of three media outlets: Magyar Hírlap as the conservative; Népszava as the left/liberal; and, finally, hvg.hu to represent the centrist opinion on migration. I only explored opinion pieces as editorials in these media outlets and used the simple keyword migráció (migration) in order to collect as many pieces as possible. Hence, taking the period from 01.06.2015 to 01.12.2018, I collected and subsequently read 91 pieces in Népszava, 232 pieces in Magyar Hírlap and 108 in hvg.hu. I read these pieces considering the narratives, slogans, and tropes that I came across as embedded in political speeches. The section on interpretations of external migration in Hungarian media below presents an overview of the most dominant themes, namely, EU institutions, European values, migration/refugees, and European identity in 50 selected opinion pieces extracted from Népszava, Magyar Hírlap, and hvg.hu.

While elaborating on the Hungarian political and media discourse on external migration, the report also notes the deeply polarized nature of Hungarian politics. This environment should generate concerns for researchers to account for full partiality when it comes to elaboration of discourse. The environment may also compromise reflexivity in data collection. However, the reflexivity problem that this report notes should be understood in view of the general concerns that discursive scholars face in their work on politically polarized contexts (Grint, 2000 in Iszatt-White 2011, 119). For us, there is value in delving deep into the context and building local knowledge around which research problems form. In order, initially, this report projected to use citizen reflections with focus groups on narratives on external migration and Europeanisation to balance media and political narrative research. However, considering the Covid-19 pandemic, as the WP6 leadership composed of GCU and OEAW, we decided

¹ TGM: A legnagyobb Orbán-rejtély (24.10.2018), available at, https://hvg.hu/itthon/20181024_TGM_A_legnagyobb_Orbanrejtely (last accessed 24.09.2020)

against holding these focus groups. Instead, the report turns to interviews with non-governmental migration actors in Hungary carried out in 2018-2019 in its conclusion to explore where they situate themselves vis-à-vis the political narrative that Fidesz has represented.

1. Party-Political Structure: History and Developments since 2011

Orbán's leadership and Fidesz's dominance of Hungarian politics have been uncontested since 2010. None of the other political parties can pose a challenge to Fidesz and the left and the liberal camp is very fragmented. However, the recent municipal and regional elections in 2019 indicate that if the opposition parties can establish electoral pacts involving left, liberal, and even extreme right forces, they can then push Fidesz back in cities. This was how the new Budapest mayor Karácsony won office in 2019. However, neither the left nor the liberal parties managed to gain much electoral success in Hungary at the national election since 2010. The April 2010 election brought a decisive defeat for both the liberal and the left-liberal camps in Hungary. The elections delivered Orbán's party a two-thirds majority in the unicameral parliament, enough to amend and eventually change the constitution. Following the election, as Orbán stated, "a new social contract evolved in the polling booths when Hungarians showed an unprecedented agreement in overthrowing the old system and decided to build a new system of national cooperation" (Speech in the Parliament June 8, 2010). Instead of liberalism that marked the making of national and international politics in Hungary, Fidesz adopted a new discursive tool pointing at alternative modernisation, based on Christian values, a strong state, and the nation. Thereafter, Fidesz engaged also in a "moral revolution" to re-acquire "Hungary's strength" vis-à-vis its liberal foes at the domestic front as well as international capital and bankers on the Western front (Korkut 2012). In this effort, its two-thirds parliamentary majority, control over the judiciary and the intermingling of the legislative and executive powers thoroughly became its fundamental sources of strength (Sárközy 2013) continuously for the past decade. In time, Orbán also adopted the image of a leader that is hard-working and engaged in a constant fight with the liberal European elites that criticize his work to strengthen Hungary as a proud European nation (Korkut 2012).

Emulating neo-authoritarianism, the Fidesz regime established a system of managed constitutional democracy that limits the role of judiciary and freedom of media, and a majoritarian democracy whose legitimacy rests on traditional family values, religion, spirituality, and patriotism as well as a constitution that provides the basis for its own neo-conservative ideology (Ladányi and Szelényi 2014). Ad hoc decisions and constant legal and policy changes have affected migration politics and implied an unqualifiedly low level of accountability. In my earlier reports on the border management regime (Gyollai and Korkut 2019) and reception policies in Hungary (Gyollai and Korkut 2020), I presented the extent to which such ad hoc decision making has affected migration policy in general and the treatment of migrants in particular.

Overall, the political regime in Hungary has placed little emphasis on the human rights of migrants, global migration challenges or Hungary's international and European commitments including the rule of law, accountability and non-interference into the humanitarian sector. In this report, I underline the political context that informed migration politics and how Hungarian politicians have framed migration politics of Hungary to support a general claim that Hungary has been a defender of Christianity and European civilization. This is the reason why it became crucial to explore where Fidesz stands vis-à-vis Europe.

In essence, Fidesz is as a political party that can harness a pragmatic and religiously-informed conservatism in order to suggest a course of Europeanisation that differs from what the party sees as the liberal course that Europeanisation followed so far. Its formal pro-EU

stance is conditioned by the realization of its own conservative vision for the EU. This does not imply unconditional support for integration, and as a result Fidesz pays a selective allegiance with EU integration as long as it helps it to fulfil its own goals. This way, it also avoids being branded an anti-EU party. This pragmatism reflects Fidesz's ideological roots in Christian conservatism. Its resulting involvement in the course of European integration, also thanks to its strong position in European People's Party, gave it further credibility even if its membership in the EPP group was suspended in 2019 following the rule of law and democracy concerns in Hungary. The EPP still upholds this suspension, but the party has not been expelled from the EPP fraction in the European Parliament.

The Fidesz leadership has always aligned their position on Europe with a Hungarian nationalism associated with Hungary's Christian traditions. Regarding the EU, as early as 1995, Orbán suggested that Hungary's historical legacy, Western Christian tradition and national values are its anchors to the continent. From 1998 onwards, the bulk of the Hungarian accession negotiations coincided with the Fidesz's earlier term in office until 2002. Furthermore, around 2002 there was an overlap between Hungary's preparation for EU accession and the millennial celebrations of St. Stephen's receiving of the Holy Crown from the Pope, a sign of Hungary's acceptance to Western Christianity, which also corresponded with Fidesz's term in office. This connection was endorsed by the Catholic Church, which presented accession as the confirmation of St. Stephen's good choice in 1000. Hence, while the Hungarians' appearance in the Carpathian basin in the late 9th century marked their arrival in Europe in geographical terms, with the achievement of statehood and receipt of the Crown they came to be seen to have arrived Europe in a cultural and political sense. Thus, Fidesz approached the Christian foundation of the state as the prototype of Hungary's "Europeanisation", and argued that the EU accession process did not require Hungarians to be remade as "European" over again. Orbán was adamant that Hungarians' cultural and civilizational performance entitled them to feel as equal partners in the community of Western democracies (Fowler 2004: 61). Moreover, Orbán insisted that Fidesz's electoral success brought an end to liberal democracy as the former failed to protect and maintain Christian culture (Korkut 2012). Later, protecting Europe became also a common trope for Fidesz to seek audiences for its migration meta-narrative.

Our success has shown that the period of liberal democracy has come to an end. It has become useless to protect human dignity, to extend freedom, and to guarantee physical security. It already cannot maintain the Christian culture. There are those in Europe who still tinker with it thinking that they can reform it. But they do not understand that it is not that the structure fell apart, but the world has changed. Our answer, the Hungarian answer to the world that has changed, is instead of the liberal democracy that ran into darkness we are to establish 21st Century Christian democracy that guarantee human dignity.²

However, Fidesz did not brand itself as an anti-European political force even if it remained sceptical of the liberal tradition that thus far affected European integration. Orbán sought to present Hungary as the true European actor with its overt concern and care for Europe's future and the security of its citizens. To this extent, he alleged that the West neither appreciated the

² Orbán Viktor beszéde a miniszterelnöki eskütételét követően (10.05.2018), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedekek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-miniszterelnoki-eskutetelet-kovetoen> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

role that Hungary has played nor engaged with Hungary to understand the true role that it has played.

Westerners, even if they admired the Hungarian revolution [in reference to 1848 revolution], did not understand [it]. They did not understand the power that works in us. They did not understand why we were fighting a force that we could hardly defeat by human calculation. They did not understand that we were fighting it because we clung to our own culture, way of life until the very end and did not want to dissolve in anyone else's crucible. We want them to respect who and what we are. We have guarded Europe's borders for a thousand years and fought for our national independence. We are a brave and warrior nation that knows well who is not respected, despised. We are not understood in Brussels today either as they did not understand us even then [at the time of the Hungarian revolution].³

In return, he sought to utilize the Hungarian EU membership in a pragmatic manner to set conditions for the future of EU integration, informed by national traditions and sovereignties, family, cohesion and Christian solidarity.

[... Europe] first rejected its roots and instead of a Europe that acts with its Christian roots, it turned to building Europe of Open Society [in reference to Soros Foundation]. In Christian Europe, work had value, humans had dignity, man and woman were equal, the family was the foundation of the nation, nation was the foundation of Europe, and states in their turn guaranteed security. In today's Europe of Open Society, there are no borders. European people are exchanged with migrants, family became co-habitation that can vary as desired, nation, national self-awareness and national feeling have negative connotations and it is considered to be excessive. In liberal Europe, to be European does not mean anything.⁴

At this juncture, Orbán presented external migration to Europe as a central threat to the pillars of EU integration. He has organised his alternative Europeanisation discourse based on the failure of "liberal" Europe, including the EU institutions, to respond to this asserted threat. Over the coming sections, I will reflect further on these aspects, considering the political speeches of Viktor Orbán that I collected for this report.

³ Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXIX. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (28.07.2018), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxix-balvanyosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban/> (last accessed 05.06.2020).

⁴ Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXIX. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (28.07.2018), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxix-balvanyosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban/> (last accessed 05.06.2020).

2. Media Structure and the Question of Europeanisation

Since 2010, the analyses on crises and socio-political change in Hungary, rule of law (Bánkuti, Halmai, Scheppele 2012, Scheppele 2013) as well as Hungary's shifting geopolitical orientation and its migration governance have featured extensively in Hungarian and western academic and media debates. Considering this debate, the empirical material of this report relies on an analysis of Viktor Orbán's formulations of external migration, essentially first the threats that it he claims to pose for Europe and Europeans and second his projections for European futures in view of external migration. Orbán's discourse and projections have not remained as indigenous solutions and not necessarily nativist. He has depicted Hungarian solutions to external migration also as an answer for European "migration problem".⁵ To this extent, Hungarian media gives extensive references to what happens in Western Europe in relation to migration at times serving Orbán's attempts to generate audiences for his discourse.

The Media, opposition parties, political colleagues and activists construct certain 'truths' about political leadership and leader effectiveness (Grint, 2000 in Iszatt-White 2011: 119). Taking these under consideration, this report nonetheless shows how Orbán has become the sole voice and authority on external migration to Hungary and Europe. Despite the deep polarization in the country between the conservative and liberal fractions, it does not appear as if the latter could present an alternative discourse to displace Orbán's eminence in the making of migration narrative. Hence, when it came to media analysis, while achieving impartiality in data collection in politically polarized contexts was my aim, the report shows that conservative-centrist-left/liberal media outlets actually did not differ too much in their evaluation of how Hungarian politicians narrativized external migration. This is important to note, given my original assumption being that these media outlets would have appealed to different audiences.

However, it is also important to note that media freedom is extensively compromised in Hungary (European Federation of Journalists, 2019), and this would possibly affect how institutional and discursive practices regarding migration politics are represented in print and digital media in Hungary. There is full control of the public media by the government. The media authority regulates the media to prevent anti-government voices. In this context, only a handful of left-liberal voices could propose a critical elaboration of Hungarian politics, including Orbán's migration discourse. An earlier and important voice of left-liberal politics, *Népszabadság*, already ceased publication in 2016. Orbán's government also tried to enhance government control over social media, with an attempt to introduce an internet tax in 2014. Although this attempt failed after protests in Hungary, a recent rule by decree (passed in March 2020) allegedly against the coronavirus crisis, has given Hungary's executive the power to control social media making "intentionally spreading false information about the coronavirus" punishable by a prison sentence of up to five years (Német, Pintér, Presinszky, 2020; Korkut and Gyollai 2020).

⁵ Orbán's victory: Migration crisis changed the game (09.04.2018), available at, <https://www.euronews.com/2018/04/09/orban-s-victory-migration-crisis-changed-the-game> (last accessed 01.10.2020).

3. Headlines and Events Impacting on Migration Discourse since 2011

The issue of external migration never lost its salience in Hungarian politics since the sudden increase in the number of migrants arriving irregularly at Europe in the summer of 2015. As I recounted above and will explore further below, it has retained its importance as an issue in Hungarian media as well. While the news content has been influenced mostly by constant changes in Hungarian institutions, law, and policy impacts that dealt with external migration, at times the external reactions that Hungary received in view of its policies also affected subsequent headlines on this issue.

A first point for consideration was the establishment of transit zones along the Hungarian-Serbian border fence. As we noted in WP4 Hungary Reception report (Gyollai and Korkut 2020), transit zones have essentially become the only reception facilities in Hungary, where they function as de-facto detention centres. As of March 2018, irregular migrants may file asylum application in the transit zones only, and they cannot leave these zones throughout the entire asylum procedure. The rule applies to everyone except unaccompanied minors below 14 (Gyollai and Korkut 2020). What is noteworthy is the lack of critical tone that I came across in the media narrative analysis on both the border fence and the transit zones. Even in the left/liberal media outlets, there was no overt criticism of these developments, but instead an insinuation that given the low number of Muslims arriving Hungary should not be under a particular security threat.

Second, one can mention the so-called “Stop Soros Act” that the Hungarian government introduced in May 2018. This legislative package comprises, inter alia, amendments to the Criminal Code that effectively criminalised NGOs, civil society actors providing humanitarian support for asylum seekers. The conservative media picked up on this more extensively than the centrist and left/liberal media. If anything, the left/liberal criticisms and commentary on this law remained tepid, considering the polarised political environment and media’s unwillingness to be branded as pro-Soros in that context.

Finally, one can mention the infringement process and Sargentini report for the European Parliament calling on the Council to determine, pursuant to Article 7(1) of the Treaty on European Union, the existence of a clear risk of a serious breach by Hungary of the values on which the Union is founded.⁶ The conservative media, in line with the political narrative, reflected on this report as an attack on Hungarian democracy and its politicians’ travails to inhibit the course of external migration targeting Hungary and the EU. As I present below, the report presented the government with an opportunity to further delineate the liberal conspiracy within the EU that targets Hungary, and the necessity of standing together to promote the role of national sovereignty in determining EU migration policy. The formulation of the political narrative and how the media picked up this narrative show the extent to which Sargentini report impacted on how politicians sought to foster amenable audiences by adopting a reactive tone.

⁶ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-8-2018-0250_EN.html

4. Political Speeches

What has been constant in Viktor Orbán’s narrative since 2015 is that migrants and refugees threaten the EU for many years to come.⁷ Orbán’s view for the future of Europe, in this sense, is that it is required to protect its borders and Hungary has an essential role to play and deliver this protection. In this respect, Orbán proposed hotspots as the most sustainable tool for migration management and proposed externalization and migration management through centres located outside the EU.⁸ It is noteworthy that the most recent EC proposals over the new EU migration and asylum pact also seeks to introduce new compulsory pre-entry screening involving health, identity and security.⁹ It takes into consideration the proposals of hard line members, including Hungary, that the focus should be on stopping migration instead of managing it. Importantly, member states, as Ruy and Yayboke (2020) recently wrote in a report for the Center for Strategic & International Studies, such as “France, Germany, Greece, and Italy (important arrival and relocation countries) have cautiously welcomed the proposal; with Germany holding the rotating Council presidency, there may be enough momentum to push this over the finish line and accommodate the more difficult members”.¹⁰

Orbán’s proposal for the future EU is that it needs to extend “security” to its citizens – especially, at the face of what Orbán indicates, given terror moving to the EU, tipping over the everyday safety of its citizens¹¹ - as its central priority. Orbán warns that Europe’s former success has made it delusional, and that the continent does not realize how it has been pushed back on the world stage without its noticing.¹² With regard to external migration, he reframes the question not as less or more Europe, but rather as a “weak” or “strong Europe”.¹³ In order to make Europe stronger, Orbán argues, border security is a must. He suggest that the Dublin protocol should primarily deal with border security rather than focusing on migrant rights: “there could be no discrepancy between migrant rights and border security”.¹⁴ However, Orbán also believes that the EU is not capable of this, given that the European elite has already declared

⁷ Orbán Viktor beszéde a miniszterek bemutatásán (18.05.2018), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-miniszterek-bemutatasan20180518> (last accessed 04.06.2020)

⁸ Orbán Viktor sajtónyilatkozata a Visegrádi Négyek kormányfőinek és Ausztria kancellárjának csúcstalálkozóján (21.06.2018), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-sajtonyilatkozata-a-visegradi-negyek-kormanyfoinek-es-ausztria-kancellarjanak-csucstalalkozojan> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

⁹ Europe migration: EU plans mandatory pact to 'rebuild trust' (23.09.2020), available at, <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-europe-54249312> (last accessed 07.10.2020)

¹⁰ Deciphering the European Union’s New Pact on Migration and Asylum (29.09.2020), available at, <https://www.csis.org/analysis/deciphering-european-unions-new-pact-migration-and-asylum> (last accessed 07.10.2020). Nepszava: 91

¹¹ Magyarország az otthonunk, meg kell védenünk! (29.09.2016), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/magyarorszag-az-otthonunk-meg-kell-vedenunk/> (last accessed 04.06.2020)

¹² Orbán Viktor ünnepi beszéde az 1956. évi forradalom és szabadságharc 61. Évfordulóján (23.10.2017), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-unnepi-beszede-az-1956-evi-forradalom-es-szabadsagharc-61-evfordulojan/> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

¹³ Orbán Viktor előadása az „Európa jövője” című V4-konferencián (26.01.2018), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-eloadasa-az-europa-jovoje-cimu-v4-konferencian/> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

¹⁴ Orbán Viktor sajtónyilatkozata Sebastian Kurzcal, Ausztria kancellárjával történt tárgyalását követően (31.01.2018), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-sajtonyilatkozata-sebastian-kurzcal-ausztria-kancellarjaval-tortent-targyalasat-kovetoen> (last accessed 05.06.2020).

“bankruptcy” and the symbol of this is the European Commission.¹⁵ He says that the EU member states are not hoping any solutions [to the problem of external migration] from the Commission, and this is why member states should take the reins in their hands to control migration.¹⁶ Thereafter, Orbán places his trust in regaining sovereignty from the EU in order to reform the EU,¹⁷ and argues that the issue is not that there is need for “more Europe” but instead a need for more national autonomy.¹⁸ This complex narrative that refers to Europeanisation, sovereignty, Europeans and their security certainly presents a series of composite discourses whence Orbán can present his politics both as an EU-phile and EU-critical.

As a member state, Orbán argues, Hungary has a major role to play. He argues that Hungary - as well as Central Europe – are Europe’s future¹⁹ with their first and foremost function of protecting the EU’s external borders.

If we have not fulfilled our duty, Europe would have fallen down already [...] We Hungarians are one of the most committed countries within the European Union. It is a different question whether we want to change the current politics or not, but our commitment towards the future of Europe is strong. That is why we intend to change [it] so that we can protect Europe, which we always felt our home and for which we already sacrificed so many. We are looking to what is west from us [to see] what happens if [they] decide without asking people on such far-reaching questions [i.e. the quota regime].²⁰

Orbán warns that migrants are watching the EU from Hungary’s southern borders what he calls with their “wolf eyes”.²¹ Thereby, he introduces the Hungarian government’s duty as the protection of Hungarians from this very threat.²² Yet despite having stated that migrants have “wolf eyes”, Orbán does not decline the obligation to extend humanitarianism. Indeed, he states that “migrants have been lured into making such dangerous journeys with the promise

¹⁵ Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXIX. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (28.07.2018), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxix-balvanyosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban/> (last accessed 05.06.2020).

¹⁶ Orbán Viktor beszéde a határvadászok eskütételén (12.01.2017), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-hatarvadaszok-eskutetelen/> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

¹⁷ Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXVIII. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (22.07.2017), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxviii-balvanyosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

¹⁸ Orbán Viktor előadása az „Európa jövője” című V4-konferencián (26.01.2018), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-eloadasa-az-europa-jovoje-cimu-v4-konferencian/> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

¹⁹ Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXVIII. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (22.07.2017), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxviii-balvanyosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

²⁰ Magyarország az otthonunk, meg kell védenünk! (29.09.2016), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/magyarorszag-az-otthonunk-meg-kell-vedenunk/> (last accessed 04.06.2020)

²¹ Orbán Viktor beszéde a rendőrtiszthelyettes-jelöltek eskütételén (14.09.2015), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-rendortiszthelyettes-jeloltek-eskutetelen> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

²² Orbán Viktor beszéde a rendőrtiszthelyettes-jelöltek eskütételén (14.09.2015), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-rendortiszthelyettes-jeloltek-eskutetelen> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

of welfare at their destinations. It is those terrorists that exploit some of those migrants' [legitimate] claims showing that migrant groups are full of conflicts".²³ This is a narrative that we noted as common in a recent article that compared humanitarianism in Italy and Hungary. Notwithstanding this humanitarian stance, Orbán still maintains the warning against the Brussels elite, the European leaders, and the Hungarian opposition who allegedly advocate that "all people that come to Europe intend to live here according to [European] customs and laws. Yet, the facts are showing the opposite".²⁴ Instead, the ideal Europe, with regard to the handling of external migration, would be the one where [security forces] retain the duty to make sure that whoever comes follows national laws²⁵.

Orbán also maintains that Hungary has been self-sufficient, and when migration reached its doors Hungary did not expect help from anyone²⁶ and Europe would have also done better had it not rejected Hungarian solutions that were both operational and useful.²⁷ Proposing that the European public needs to be heard, Orbán states that "we don't know what Europeans think about migration, but we certainly know what their leaders think".²⁸ Once again, with his narrative, Orbán seeks to present himself and the migration politics of the Hungarian government as "pro-European", in an attempt to establish a direct link with European publics, capturing a continent-wide disenchantment with the elite.

Orbán presents what the European elite has done on migration politics so far as "hurry-scurry" that led to chaos,²⁹ and suggests that European institutions, faced with the [migratory] movement of people, has resigned and accepted that migration cannot be stopped and that they cannot do anything against it. To this extent, according to Orbán, many instead look into

²³ Magyarország az otthonunk, meg kell védenünk! (29.09.2016), available at, [http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/magyarország-az-otthonunk-meg-kell-vedenunk/\(last](http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/magyarország-az-otthonunk-meg-kell-vedenunk/(last) accessed 04.06.2020)

²⁴ Orbán Viktor beszéde a határvadászok eskütételén (12.01.2017), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-hatarvadaszok-eskutetelen/> (last accessed 04.06.2020). Orbán Viktor beszéde a határvadászok eskütételén (07.03.2017), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-hatarvadaszok-eskutetelen-2/> (last accessed 04.06.2020); Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXVIII. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (22.07.2017), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxviii-balvan-yosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban> (last accessed 04.06.2020); Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXIX. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (28.07.2018), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxix-balvan-yosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban/> (last accessed 05.06.2020).

²⁵ Orbán Viktor beszéde a rendőrtiszthelyettes-jelöltek eskütételén (14.09.2015), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-rendortiszthelyettes-jeloltek-eskutetelen> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

²⁶ Orbán Viktor beszéde a rendőr tiszthelyettesek eskütételén (17 June 2017), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-rendor-tiszthelyettesek-eskutetelen/> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

²⁷ Orbán Viktor beszéde a határvadászok eskütételén (12.01.2017), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-hatarvadaszok-eskutetelen/> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

²⁸ Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXVIII. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (22.07.2017), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxviii-balvan-yosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

²⁹ Orbán Viktor sajtónyilatkozata a Visegrádi Négyek kormányfőinek és Ausztria kancellárjának csúcstalálkozóján (21.06.2018), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-sajtonyilatkozata-a-visegradi-negyek-kormanyfoinek-es-ausztria-kancellarjanak-csucstalalkozojan> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

distributing “millions of “illegal” migrants as a solution”.³⁰ Yet, it is rather “more humanitarian not to accept them [those without the refugee status] into the EU than having them on the European territory for a few years and force removal in a few years”.³¹ Orbán continues to state that “we do not know what is successful integration”³² yet we know that migration is the Trojan horse of terrorism.³³ In the end, the EU needs to come back to its senses.³⁴ The future course of Europeanisation and the role that the member states can play in effect is then as follows.

We need the [European] Union and the union needs us. That is why we are ready to take part in those changes as a constituent that the Union cannot evade. With all our strength we will represent that the Union should work as an alliance of free nations and drop any nightmares towards European United States. The European Union needs to come back to the fields of reality. At first, there needs a change in conceptualisations of migration. Today, in Brussels they think that it is unfair if a person were born in a place where he or she does not want to live. They think that they should receive rights to move wherever they want to live. In Brussels, thousands of paid activists, bureaucrats, and politicians work so that migration becomes a fundamental human right. For that they want to take away from us the right that we decide who we accept and whom we do not. I believe that migration leads to disintegration of nations and states. The national language weakens, the borders wither away, the national culture falls apart, and only one open society remains. Eventually, the integration of the European societies would develop to an extent that it may result in the establishment of one single and united European government. This is the destiny of those who do not protect themselves from migration. Even if not tomorrow, but in the not too far future. This is how they play the game, this is their master plan. I am not offering you pap with a hatchet. I make it clear to you, here and now, that my government is against the process, and all the inner stages, that lead to this plan, and we firmly stand up against it in the name of Hungarian freedom. Multiculturalism was the first step. Political correctness restricting the right to freedom of expression was the next. This is where Europe stands today. The third step would be the mandatory resettlement quota. In order to prevent the Europe we love, and are ready to make serious sacrifice for, from further proceeding on the path of self-destruction, we must, and we will take our stance on the European political battlefield. We are against the resettlement quota; we stand up for the Christian culture and fight for to protect our borders.

³⁰ Magyarország az otthonunk, meg kell védenünk! (29.09.2016), available at, [http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/magyarorszag-az-otthonunk-meg-kell-vedenunk/\(last](http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/magyarorszag-az-otthonunk-meg-kell-vedenunk/(last) accessed 04.06.2020)

³¹ Orbán Viktor sajtónyilatkozata az Európai Tanács ülését követően (21.10.2016), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-saitonyilatkozata-az-europai-tanacs-uleset-kovetoen> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

³² Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXVIII. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (22.07.2017), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxviii-balvanyosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

³³ Orbán Viktor beszéde a határvadászok eskütételén (07.03.2017), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-hatarvadaszok-eskutetelen-2/> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

³⁴ Orbán Viktor beszéde a miniszterelnöki eskütételét követően (10.05.2018), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-miniszterelnoki-eskutetelet-kovetoen> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

While humanitarianism emerges in Orbán’s discourse, in the sense that Hungary extends help when there is a need in the form of overseas development assistance,³⁵ still he considers that it is more humane to keep migrants at bay – in hotspots beyond EU’s borders.³⁶ In any case, he argues, “when people with conflicting aims arrive at a community or a country, this does not bring integration but just chaos”.³⁷ In order to prevent this, Orbán argues, every EU country needs to protect its borders and should make it clear to migrants they will be sent back if they arrive at the EU “unlawfully”. Orbán calls for the EU to have its own military to protect itself,³⁸ and has called for military solutions to external migration as he appealed to Hungarian security forces.

You are now defending the borders of Europe as it happened for the past 500 years. Protecting ourselves and Europe also. This became the national fate of the Hungarian nation over centuries [...] The era of naivety, illusions and laxity have closed in Europe [...] There are those who think that all people that come to Europe intend to live here according to our customs and laws. The facts are showing the opposite. Terror attacks, riots, violence, crime, ethnic and cultural clashes raise our attention that those who come here do not want to live our lives, but continue with their own lives, but at the level of European people’s quality of life or within those countries that the Brussels bureaucrats intend to distribute them.³⁹

Considering this debate above, it is evident that Orbán retains what he interprets as a pro-European stance, and against that he depicts external migration as a “threat”. He proposes solutions based on national sovereignty to promote those policies that Hungary enacted as a solution. He maintains a criticism of other EU national elites but primarily focuses on the European Commission – or EU bureaucrats – whom he considers being at the root of the crisis that Europeanisation experiences facing the volume of irregular external migration.

³⁵ Magyarország az otthonunk, meg kell védenünk! (29.09.2016), available at, [http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/magyarorszag-az-otthonunk-meg-kell-vedenunk/\(last](http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/magyarorszag-az-otthonunk-meg-kell-vedenunk/(last) accessed 04.06.2020)

³⁶ Orbán Viktor sajtónyilatkozata az Európai Tanács ülését követően (21.10.2016), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedekek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-sajtonyilatkozata-az-europai-tanacs-uleset-kovetoen> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

³⁷ Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXVIII. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (22.07.2017), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedekek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxviii-balvanyosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

³⁸ Orbán Viktor beszéde a XXVIII. Bálványosi Nyári Szabadegyetem és Diáktáborban (22.07.2017), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedekek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-xxviii-balvanyosi-nyari-szabadegyetem-es-diaktaborban> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

³⁹ Orbán Viktor beszéde a határvadászok eskütételén (12.01.2017), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-hatarvadaszok-eskutetelen/> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

5. Circulation of Narratives in the Mainstream Media

This report reviewed three media sources including two daily print media as well as one internet-based news outlet in Hungary. I selected these outlets to represent the conservative, left-liberal, and mainstream voices in the Hungarian media. The WP6 Respond project considered media as a main motor for audience-making in support of an alternative conceptualisation of Europeanisation that seeks to re-write the course of “liberal Europeanisation” to respond to an imagined threat of external migration. This section primarily examines how the mainstream media circulated the narratives that Hungarian politicians introduced in response to external migration. It also traces to what extent the ideological position of the selected media source affected the way they narrated external migration and sought to generate amenable audiences for the political discourse put in circulation. The section organises its review of media narratives under the following headings: EU institutions, European values, migration/refugees, and finally identity frames.

EU institutions

The main dichotomy between the conservative and the left-liberal media with respect to the EU and external migration is whether it is the nation-state (conservative media) or the supra-national institutions of the EU such as the European Commission that should take the lead managing migration. The way the political discourse entered into media narratives and polarised opinions in the media with respect to migration management is quite clear to this extent. While the conservative media endorsed Orbán’s discourse on the important role that the EU member nation states should play in response to external migration, the left-liberal media was clear with its message that in order to have a strong EU, the EU institutions should play pivotal roles in migration management.

To this extent, it is also noteworthy that the conservative media utilised further tropes and metaphors in order to boost the resonance of Orbán’s discourse on how the EU institutions failed at the face of external migration. Magyar Hírlap called the EU Commission the “clown in Brussels” and alleged that it sought the exchange of native nations of Europe for a population with different culture, religion, and lifestyle (HUN-M4-2018). The newspaper presented the Commission as an ever-growing bureaucracy (HUN-M4-2018) and the European Parliament as “a bandwagon of the Commission” (HUN-M36-2017), as distant and as obstructive to true European identity.

Nowadays, the biggest problem is that the liberal and socialist leaders of the economic and political union which calls itself European more and more distance themselves from the moral, cultural and intellectual roots of Europe. And, by placing their own power interests above all else, they do not even respect the agreements they ratified, but obstruct true Europeans and democrats. Thus, although the winter cold weather will soon be over, we shall, unfortunately prepare ourselves, as the cold war in Europe has just started (HUN-M36-2016).

It positioned this distant Brussels jurisdiction vis-à-vis the nation states that represented true sovereignty of European peoples (HUN-M9-2018) and that were the last bastions against migrants (HUN-M8-2018). It proposed that “since the questions at stake concern the future of Europe at least; there is nothing left for the nation states but to deny their jurisdiction if they can or try to cooperate in order to change the situation” (HUN-M9-2018). In return, the left-

liberal media called for the EU to “improve the quality of life by [finding] common solutions” to common problems (HUN-M21-2018) and to adopt “morally comprehensive arguments and well-considered ideas” (HUN-M26-2017). There was a stronger emphasis on integration in order to cure the weaknesses of Europe vis-à-vis its internal – such as Orbán and external namely Russia – foes (HUN-M31-2017).

Finally, the conservative media portrayed the strong leader (namely Orbán) alongside the strong nation state to make Europe stronger (HUN-M4-2018) as well impinging on the defense of Hungary (and the entire Southern Schengen border) as the last bastion against migrants (HUN-M8-2018) and as Europe’s future (HUN-M9-2018). Orbán’s narrative that Hungary was the future of Europe was commonly picked to this extent. The adoration of Orbán as the leader with a unique foresight was also very clear as the following quotation shows: “the leader of our country could see the future better and judge the situation caused by migration more accurately (than the EU), and – accordingly – it was he who first used the defense against migration as political weapon” (HUN-M17-2018).

European Values

Strengthening Europe and reinforcing it through Christian democracy (HUN-M1-2018) appears as a pinnacle requisite for protecting European values facing external migration in the conservative media. The conservative media praised Europe as a strong civilisation with firm foundations that can go rotten only from inside (HUN-M3-2018), reflecting on the liberal direction imposed on Europe by the EC and liberal European leaders. Yet, those who reject external migration still aimed to portray themselves as the true humanitarians.

The fight for the European identity and traditions has nothing to do with inhumanity. It is about the love of our own people. Precisely those who support migration are responsible for the death of migrants drown in water and of the victims of terror attacks in Europe (HUN-M8-2018).

In effect, the most humanitarian – and Christian – solution is to create reception centres in North Africa funded by the EU (HUN-M11-2018). This was yet another political slogan that the media picked from Orbán. The centrist media, in return, calls this “desperate goodwill of the powerful”, and intimates that what would make Europe strong is not mere criticism of its leaders (namely Orbán), but action to guarantee peace in Europe and the security of the European citizens (HUN-M25-2018). The conservative media also presents Orbán, Wilders, and Farage as the vanguard against the “self-destroying and idiotic migration politics of the EU” as they stand to protect “home” against “supranationalism” of the EU (HUN-M41-2018). This appears as an attempt to create pan-European audiences – though in Hungarian language – for the policies that Hungary enacted against external migration. The debate in media goes as follows: “Who would deny that the biggest issue of debate in European politics is: whose Europe are we going to build? The Europe of states, the Europe of nations, perhaps the Europe of people?” (HUN-M42-2018)

Migration/Refugees

It is noteworthy that, regardless of ideological colour, all conservative, left-liberal and centrist media elaborated on the theme of “danger” that migrants and refugees posed to Europe. This is in line with my proposition above that the lack of a tangible opposition with

alternative migration politics was what made Orbán's discourse of external migration so resonant and dominant in Hungary. Only Tamás Gáspár Miklós, a progressive left-wing essayist and a strong voice in Hungarian media, was forthcoming on this when he wrote "each and every opposition party, even if not cheerfully but still, supports Viktor Orbán's (to phrase it in a polite and moderate way) racist asylum- and fence policy" (HUN-M22-2018). This was also one instance where the border fence and transit zones were picked up in the media.

Conservative and other media outlets referred to migrants and migration using consistent metaphors and tropes. "Alien hordes running over European nations ... bringing brutal violence" threatening women, elderly, and car owners (HUN-M2-2018) as well as forces accelerating the mental decline of Europeans suffering from severe depression (HUN-M7-2018). The media also paid attention to "Europeans going extinct", having "no children" leading to a type of "collective suicide" (HUN-M44-2016). In this respect, not only protection and reception that may be extended to newcomers appeared troublesome, but also the integration of migrants with different cultural and religious backgrounds (HUN-M12-2016). Along with Orbán, also Lajos Kósa, a well-known Fidesz mayor of the city of Debrecen in eastern Hungary, featured to note how "illegal migration increased terror threat and the risk of crime" (HUN-M15-2015). In order to create the audience that the political narrative needed, one quotation in the conservative media read as follows: "A vast amount of sensible European civilians agree there are lines that cannot be crossed. The European soil, the living space of European people cannot be surrendered to invaders" (HUN-M43-2016).

The left-liberal media, in its turn, reflected on "Islamic terror" as well in relation to migration but adopted a more humanitarian tone stating that "it should be eliminated in order to prevent the hundreds of thousands (millions) of asylum-seekers being forced to leave their home" (HUN-M16-2015). To illustrate how similarly conservative and left-liberal media imagined external migration, consider the following quote from the left/liberal paper *Népszava*:

Yes, they (the majority of the population) agree that migration poses a serious threat to Hungary's interests, and that the PM is right when – talking in first person – sending more soldiers to the border and having new defense lines constructed. That is, the dangerousness of Orbán's speech lies in the fact that the majority of the people – perhaps the European people – are concerned about the migratory flows which he calls "népvándorlás". We neither should underestimate the threat itself, nor the impact of such speeches (HUN-M14-2016).

Therefore, centrist media drew from the political narrative in deploying the "trouble" narrative of migrants, but also criticised the same narrative. I came across the following quotation noting that the migrants would stay and become a burden and "no matter how troublesome [sending them back] is, it would be doable for Hungary" (HUN-M19-2015). In terms of the "trouble" that migrants pose, the centrist media is not reticent to note "the cultural and civilizational price of migration, the spillover of radical Islamism, the undeniable emergence of parallel societies" (HUN-M20-2018). The Hungarian weekly *HVG* to this extent praised "the fence [that] defended [the Hungarians] from all migratory pressure" (HUN-M23-2018). The same media source, while critical of Orbán, suggested that "there are no-go zones in Europe, parallel Muslim societies exist, mass migration creates excessive tension in European societies, and there are embarrassing NGOs in the Adriatic Sea" (HUN-M26-2018) and continued that "it is, of course, hard to foresee what the impact of the criticism of the EU's wrong political decisions, its clumsiness and of Merkel's mistakes would be on our nation. They

say: neither Brussels, nor Berlin gets easily offended, politics and diplomacy is not for the faint-hearted”.

Identity Frames

In all three Hungarian newspapers, there is a manifest identification of migrants with Islam and, as its extension, terrorism. All media outlets from the three ideological spectra that I analysed took this for granted. Magyar Hírlap put this assumption in the most straightforward manner as follows: “even the monkey knows exactly: red button = banana, terror = Islamist” (HUN-M38-2016). In an essentialist manner, migrants are depicted as “individuals completely alien to the traditions and values of the continent” (HUN-M5-2018). In terms of how this may affect the future of Europe, there is a widespread tone of warning embellished with the most prominent trope that nation states should decide EU’s migration policy rather than the Commission. The conservative media further belittled the Commission when it proposed the quota regime as a pan-European solution writing that the “EU keeps pushing the quota resettlement; even if [this is when] things go according to the migrants’ expectation and not that of the pea-brained politicians” (HUN-M35-2017).

As discussed previously, the security-focused tone of the conservative media, which frequently borders on racism, is reproduced in identity frames. However, what is more crucial is how the centrist and left/liberal media positioned themselves vis-à-vis this evident political emphasis on security. In terms of identity frames, the latter media also take it for granted that the Muslims represent migrants *per se*, and they are by definition a possible source of danger. Yet, they can also have benefits particularly in view of the aging population in Europe. As a result, the following, which may be read as pro-migration at a first glance, in fact shows that an essentialist tone is evident in the left-liberal media as well.

In case of Hungary, for example, we are talking about hardly more than 1200 Syrian asylum applications to process [in reference to EC’s settlement quota proposals] and not about their automatic entry. Given this low number, I suppose, we are not threatened by Islamisation even if all of them were granted asylum (HUN-M12-2016).

In this case the author assesses the danger of Islamisation with the number of Muslims resident in a country. Furthermore, they do not look at migrants as individuals but Muslim. They consider all Muslims with the proclivity to “Islamise” the societies where they are in. A further example reads in left-liberal media as follows. “We are not a target country [for Muslim migration]. Thus, it would be sensible, if these target countries tried to defend themselves against the migratory flows, even with harsh measures, and we can afford to behave in a more humane way” (HUN-M18-2015). As with the example above, this one is also taken from Népszava, a left-liberal media outlet. The author again takes it for granted that Muslim migration is a process to be defended from, and hence looks for reasons to justify why “target countries” may wish to defend themselves. Yet, “as Hungary is not a “target country”, they argue, “Hungary can act in a more humane way” (HUN-M18-2015).

Conclusions

What do we learn about a conservative conceptualisation of Europeanisation that rejects nominally liberal European migration policies looking at Hungary? The case of Hungary and particularly Fidesz under Orbán show that conservative value orientations and ideologies for the future shape of the EU gain resonance but not necessarily adopt a Eurosceptical political strategy. Europragmatism is the case if the political parties are to simultaneously interrelate their national political priorities and their visions for the future course of European integration. To an extent that the political parties interrelate their priorities and visions, they can create rooms for an *à la carte* appraisal of Europeanisation pending on their domestic agendas. This means that politicians may associate positive qualifications to Europe as long as first, they can append the preservation of their states' national characters to the course of EU integration and second, their European credentials provide an upper hand against their political rivals. The result is that they project their own values to the future shape of the EU while vying for a 'domesticized' union. That is how political parties tend to adopt ambiguous stances towards the course of integration (Kopecký and Mudde 2002).

Yet, it is not an ambiguity for the future of European integration that Europragmatism literature claimed that makes Fidesz sceptical, but rather its pursuit of EU's adopting policies promoting Fidesz's own ideological priorities for Hungary and Europe. Migration policy is a crucial example of this political stance. Orbán has not been reticent to prioritize 'national consciousness' but equally has been an adamant supporter of European integration and the rightful role of Hungary in this process. Fidesz even gains an unwarranted advantage vis-à-vis its domestic and European political rivals in this process through presenting itself as the true European. It is a proponent of social homogeneity as the basis of social solidarity in Europe and it portrays the European project-to-be along the shape of its own conservative ideology. The two quotations from Orbán to this extent are still telling in terms of how the end of liberal democracy for Europe would open space for a conservative course of Europeanisation.

Our success has shown that the period of liberal democracy has come to an end. It has become useless to protect human dignity, to extend freedom, and to guarantee physical security. It already cannot maintain the Christian culture. There are those in Europe who still tinker with it thinking that they can reform it. But they do not understand that it is not that the structure fell apart, but the world has changed. Our answer, the Hungarian answer to the world that has changed is, instead of the liberal democracy that ran into darkness instead we are to establish 21st Century Christian democracy that guarantee human dignity.⁴⁰

We want such Hungary and Europe where it is proud and recognised to be Hungary, where customs, history and culture are respected. We Hungarian want such Europe where we can like our own Hungarian life.⁴¹

⁴⁰ Orbán Viktor beszéde a miniszterelnöki eskütételét követően (10.05.2018), available at, <https://www.kormany.hu/hu/a-miniszterelnok/beszedek-publikaciok-interjuk/orban-viktor-beszede-a-miniszterelnoki-eskutetelet-kovetoen> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

⁴¹ Orbán Viktor beszéde a határvadászok eskütételén (07.03.2017), available at, <http://www.miniszterelnok.hu/orban-viktor-beszede-a-hatarvadaszok-eskutetelen-2/> (last accessed 04.06.2020).

While the report originally aspired to trace the resonance of these discourses across public audiences, due to the pandemic we could not hold the planned focus groups. However, in order to have a glimpse of the resonance that Orbán's discourse has gained, I explored the theme of Europe and external migration in our interviews with the civil sector in Hungary between 2018 and 2019. Notice that the civil sector interviewees were active parties in delivering migrant integration support during the course of the interviews and hence would have felt the brunt of anti-migration policies of the government.

Overall, they reflected on how Hungary managed to pursue a “hardcore” migration policy in the EU, veering away from established EU norms and presenting European structures as overburdened. In a nutshell, they stated, the dominant narrative in Hungary suggested that Hungary opposes the European system of refugee reception, but instead portrays a Hungarian vision for the rest of Europe, that is, based on the highly controlled reception system established in Hungary (Interview 3). In this attempt, Hungarian leaders endeavored to portray, both to the rest of Europe and to the Hungarian public, that the Hungarian system is not all that different from the practices in other EU countries. In a way, they raised attention to particular events in Italy or France and pursued a form of *whataboutism* to justify de-humanizing practices against asylum-seekers in Hungary (Interview 6). Furthermore, as a result of the differences between member-state and EU priorities and their overall disparity, the projects and services set at the EU level do not extend to member-states (Interview 5). This caused one of our interviewees to indicate that there is no EU-level of migration management at all and what goes on in Hungary contravenes all international migration treaties (Interview 8). In this muddled system of migration governance, Orbán consolidates his own conservative migration and Europeanisation narrative as an alternative to the liberal course of Europeanisation that held sway in the EU for decades. In a way, the new “Promoting the European way of Life” agenda and the EU Pact on migration and asylum give indications that Orbán's conservative agenda for the future course of Europeanisation has resonated extensively in Brussels.

References

- Bánkuti, M.; Halmi, G. and Scheppele, K.L. (2012). Hungary's Illiberal Turn: Disabling the Constitution. *Journal of Democracy*, 23(3): 138-46. Available online at: <https://www.journalofdemocracy.org/articles/hungarys-illiberal-turn-disabling-the-constitution/>
- European Federation of Journalists (2019). New report: Hungary dismantles media freedom and pluralism, 12 March, Available online at: <https://europeanjournalists.org/blog/2019/12/03/new-report-hungary-dismantles-media-freedom-and-pluralism/>.
- Fowler, B. (2004). Nation, State, Europe and national revival in Hungarian party politics: the case of the millennial commemorations, *Europe-Asia Studies*, 56(1): 57-83, DOI: [10.1080/0966813032000161446](https://doi.org/10.1080/0966813032000161446)
- Grint, K. (2000). *The Art of Leadership*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Gyollai, D. and Korkut, U. (2019) Border Management and Migration Controls in Hungary Report, 4 July, Available at: <https://respondmigration.com/wp-blog/2019/2/15/comparative-dataset-on-migration-border-management-and-migration-controls-hungary?rq=gyollai>
- (2020) Reception Policies, Practices, and Responses: Hungary Country Report, 9 March, Available at: <https://respondmigration.com/wp-blog/refugee-reception-policies-practices-responses-hungary-country-report?rq=gyollai>
- Iszatt-White, M. (2011). Methodological crises and contextual solutions: An ethnomethodologically informed approach to understanding relationship. *Leadership* 7(2): 119-135.
- Kopecký, Petr and Mudde, Cas (2002), 'The Two Sides of Eurocepticism', *European Union Politics* 3: 297-326.
- Korkut, U. (2012). *Liberalization Challenges in Hungary: Elitism, Progressivism and Populism*. New York: Palgrave.
- Korkut, U. and Gyollai, D. (2020). Crisis governance and the quest for alternative Europeanisation in Hungary, Policy Brief, June 19, Available online at: <https://respondmigration.com/policy-briefs/crisis-governance-and-the-quest-for-alternative-europeanisation-in-hungary>
- Nagel, A. (2020). Conflicting Conceptualisations of Europeanisation: Germany Country Report, 23 October, Available online at <https://respondmigration.com/wp-blog/conflicting-conceptualisations-of-europeanisation>
- Ladányi, J. and Szelényi, I. (2014). Posztkommunista neokonzervativizmus. *Élet és Irodalom*, 21 February.
- Marchesi and Terlizzi (2020). Conflicting Conceptualisations of Europeanisation – Italy Country Report, forthcoming
- Nagel, A.K. (2020). Conflicting Conceptualisations of Europeanisation – Germany Country Report, Respond Working Papers, Available online at: <https://zenodo.org/record/4103205#.X5G7GUJKjVo>.
- Német, T.; Pintér, L. and Presinszky, J. (2020). "Megszavazta az Országgyűlés a koronavírus-törvényt, Áder pedig ki is hirdette", Index.hu 16 April 2020. Available online at, https://index.hu/belfold/2020/03/30/koronavirus-torveny_koronavirus_szavazas_parlament/
- Prime Minister's Office (2010). Package of Economic Measures Announced by Dr. Viktor Orbán. 8 June. Available online at: <https://2010-2014.kormany.hu/en/prime-minister-s-office/news/package-of-economic-measures-announced-by-dr-viktor-orban>.

- Ruy, D. and Yayboke, E. (2020). Deciphering the European Union's New Pact on Migration and Asylum, CSIS, 29 September. Available online at:
<https://www.csis.org/analysis/deciphering-european-unions-new-pact-migration-and-asylum>
- Sárközy, T. (2013). A "vezérdemokracia" kormányzásának jellemzői. *Mozgó Világ* 2013/9: 19-39.
- Scheppele, K.L. (2013). The Rule of Law and the Frankenstate: Why Governance Checklists Do Not Work, *Governance*, 26(4): 559-562.
DOI: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/gove.12049>
- Szczerbiak, A. and Taggart, P. (eds.), *Opposing Europe? The Comparative Party Politics of Euroscepticism*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Appendix 1⁴²

EU Institutions	European values	Migration/refugees	Identity frames
<p>(HUN-M4-2018). Even if the clowns in Brussels pull yet another music instrument out of their sleeves, more and more begin to realise that the song remains the same: the facilitation, support and management of mass migration, because their ultimate goal is the exchange of the native nations of Europe for a population with different culture, religion and lifestyle.</p> <p>(HUN-M8-2018) In opposition to the growing bureaucracy in Brussels, more and more strong leader and social movement will emerge, who will restore Europe's status in world politics. A strong Europe can only be built upon strong nation states, this is what the Hungarian government, and more and more recently established political platforms argue. Efforts to destroy</p>	<p>(HUN-M1-2018) According to the Hungarian PM, Christian democracy is the only way to proceed for the largest party group in the EP, to reinforce the Europe of nations – there is no other way, “Europe will either be a Europe of nations, or will disappear”.</p> <p>(HUN-M3-2018). Because a civilization, which has been built on such firm foundation as Europe has, cannot be concurred from the outside, it must go rotten from the inside first.</p> <p>(HUN-M8-2018). The fight for the European identity and traditions has nothing to do with inhumanity, it is about the love of our own people. Precisely those who support migration are responsible for the death of migrants drown in water and of the victims of terror attacks in Europe.</p>	<p>(HUN-M2- 2018). Alien hordes run over our nations, many of whom are genuinely (and not just allegedly) criminal: wherever they go, they bring brutal violence, such as attacking women, slitting the throat of elderly people, mass murder or car assassinations.</p> <p>(HUN-M6-2018). Salvini and Orban have long agreed on a question with fundamental importance: in order to defend Europe and to overcome illegal migration, the borders must be defended above all else. Hungary has successfully achieved this at the land borders, while Italy has been fighting at sea.</p> <p>(HUN-M7-2018). Mass migration might accelerate not only the mental decline of Europe suffering from severe depression, but also the extinction of – just like that of the Native Americans</p>	<p>(HUN-M5-2018). Concerning the future of Europe, it is not a pressing question at all whether a prime minister joined (or not) the gay pride. Conversely, it is far more relevant that they (the EU) want to solve the problem of labour shortage with individuals completely alien to the traditions and values of the continent.</p> <p>(HUN-M12-2016). In case of Hungary, for example, we are talking about hardly more than 1200 Syrian asylum applications to process and not about their automatic entry. Given this low number, I suppose, we are not threatened by Islamisation even if all of them were granted asylum.</p> <p>(HUN-M18-2015). The Muslim immigration (and any immigration) is disproportionate, the target countries are Germany,</p>

⁴² Nepszava: 91 (01.06.2015-01.12.2018) <https://nepszava.hu/keres?s=migracio&start=2015.06.01&end=2018.12.01&author=0&rovat=7>; Magyar Hirlap: 232 (03.06.2015-30.11.2018) <https://www.magyarhirlap.hu/kereses?kifejezes=migracio&rovat=%5B%22o%22%5D&tol=2015-06-03&iq=2018-11-30&page=5>; HVG: 108 (01.06.2015-30.12.2018) <https://hvg.hu/kereses?mit=migracio&tol=2015.+06.+01.&iq=2018.+12.+31.&rovat=velemeny>

<p>sovereignty have never made Europe stronger.</p> <p>(HUN-M8-2018).</p> <p>The first migrant quota proposal was a test only; in reality they (the EU) want to force us to apply an automatic relocation mechanism, thus destroying the last bastions against migrants.</p> <p>(HUN-M9-2018).</p> <p>The stance of the supranational organizations on migration has not been changed, and they all try to take advantage of that (sic) at the expense of the sovereignty of nations. The only difference is what size of a whip they hold (it's not clear who the author means). Since the questions at stake concern the future of Europe at least; there is nothing left for the nation states but to deny their jurisdiction if they can, or try to cooperate in order to change the situation.</p> <p>(HUN-M10-2018).</p> <p>It is quite sad that the EU, apparently, forgot about the solidarity towards the Roma who have lived with us for centuries, about the support of the</p>	<p>(HUN-M11-2018).</p> <p>The Christian warrior political group represented by Orbán-Kaczynski-Salvini denies support for the vulnerable in our name, their most Christian solution is to create reception centers in Northern African countries on EU budget, though no one has shown interest yet. They (EP) will vote on the UN migration pact in December, which is already rejected by Poland as well, just like by Hungary. Morawiecki's vote is not our business, but we still can let Viktor Orban know: not in my name!</p> <p>(HUN-M13-2016).</p> <p>The desperate goodwill of the powerful is now illuminating, which gets rid of the traditions of institutionalized civil rights, and it's only due to our ideological incapacity/narrow-mindedness that we tend to see a correlation between the compulsory Danish grunting and the Hungarian fence</p> <p>[...]</p> <p>(HUN-M25-2018).</p> <p>The European community will be functional if and only if it complies with and enforces its rules and</p>	<p>following the discovery of America – the entire native population.</p> <p>(HUN-M12-2016).</p> <p>Nobody wants mass resettlement to Europe, especially not to countries with no experience in settlement and the troublesome integration of immigrants with different cultural and religious background, but it is not even at stake concerning the Visegrad countries.</p> <p>(HUN-M15-2015).</p> <p>He (Kosa) also mentioned that illegal migration increases terror threat and the risk of crime, which is true, though not in the sense cited by these politicians in the government's propaganda.</p> <p>(HUN-M16-2015).</p> <p>In my opinion, we should not take on the challenge of mass migration at the southern borders of Hungary, but much further than that; perhaps the Islamic terrorism should be eliminated in order to prevent the hundreds of thousands (billions) asylum seekers being forced to leave their home.</p> <p>(HUN-M14-2016).</p>	<p>France, Holland, England and the Scandinavian countries, especially the big cities. These countries might have to consider the consequences of the ethnic redistribution. This is not the case here, we are not a target country. Thus, it would be sensible, if these target countries tried to defend themselves against the migratory flows, even with harsh measures, and we can afford to behave in a more human way.</p> <p>(HUN-M18-2015).</p> <p>Anyone who has ever been to big cities in Western Europe, such as London, Rotterdam, Paris or Brussels knows that people of color have been present in these places in large numbers for decades, which cities could not even function without people of different cultural background. There are conflicts, Muslim fanatics occasionally light synagogues on fire, the respect for human rights is less important for them, the oppression of women is significant, etc: though white Christian fanatics are equally dangerous. The majority of Muslims have integrated into the European society, many of whom live a comfortable, middle-class life. The coexistence, as we know, is not easy, but we also know that</p>
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<p>community sometimes also referred to as a “secret asset”, and reallocated the funds originally designated for that purpose to migration.</p> <p>(HUN-M17-2015).</p> <p>The leader of our country could see the future better and judge the situation caused by migration more accurately (than the EU), and – accordingly – it was he who first used the defense against migration as political weapon.</p> <p>(HUN-M21-2018).</p> <p>The democratic forces of Central Europe, besides migration issues, have to focus on public policy matters whereby the EU could improve the quality of life by common solutions, such as joining the European Public Prosecutor’s Office, the Energy Union strategy, or the reinforced EU border control. These initiatives are all rejected by the Hungarian government due to strategical considerations, though portrayed as claims of national sovereignty.</p> <p>(HUN-M26-2018).</p> <p>The cultural and political struggle within the EU, the spillover of the nationalist- and left-wing populist parties would all be unimaginable,</p>	<p>adheres to its fundamental values. A strong Europe would not only criticize the unlawful acts of leaders such as Orban, but would also guarantee the piece in Europe and the security of the European citizens.</p> <p>(HUN-M25-2018).</p> <p>If the EU keeps failing to get a grasp on Orban and act, the illiberal allies will get closer and closer to their goal: a coward, diverging and dysfunctional Europe.</p> <p>(HUN-M29-2018).</p> <p>The Western European taxpayers finance a regime with thousands of billions, that has been fighting a “freedom-fight” against them, and has established an atmosphere, right in the middle of Europe, in total contradiction with the European values, which is: anti- and illiberal, autocratic, market-phobic, anti-individualist and state-dependent.</p> <p>(HUN-M41-2016).</p> <p>They (Orban, Wilders, Farage) reject the self-destroying and idiotic migration politics of the EU, and, according to the recent, totally unrealistic “liberal” interpretation,</p>	<p>Yes, they (the majority of the population) agree that migration poses a serious threat to Hungary’s interests, and that the PM is right when – talking in first person – sending more soldiers to the border and having new defense lines constructed. That is, the dangerousness of Orban’s speech lies in the fact that the majority of the people – perhaps the European people – are concerned about the migratory flows which he calls “nepvandorlas”. We neither should underestimate the threat itself, nor the impact of such speeches. It is, of course, hard to foresee what the impact of the criticism of the EU’s wrong political decisions, its clumsiness and of Merkel’s mistakes would be on our nation. They say: neither Brussels, nor Berlin gets easily offended, politics and diplomacy is not for the faint-hearted</p> <p>(HUN-M19-2015).</p> <p>It is, again, just a lie of the government’s propaganda (and of the Jobbik) that these people would stay with us as a burden. For example, people arriving from Kosovo, Pakistan or Bangladesh, as these countries are not war-torn, are usually sent back from Europe. No matter how</p>	<p>the ageing Europe would not be able to function without them.</p> <p>(HUN-M32-2017).</p> <p>In opposition to the idea of the open society, which, as it should now be clear from the above, originates from the Jews’ fear of the nationalism of the nation-state, a framework should be developed which, on the one hand, protects the historical and cultural heritage of the majority, and its national sovereignty (enshrined in international treaties), and guarantees the security and the preservation of the identity of the integrated but not assimilated minorities. To develop such frameworks, think tanks are needed, for example that of a joint university of the Visegrad Four, such as the Jagellonian University as a historical example. Furthermore, networks, research centres, media and NGOs that are able to introduce a new concept of Europe to the European citizens.</p> <p>(HUN-M33-2017).</p> <p>This is why Viktor Orban wrote that the European project “got stuck on the track” in the Hungarian Review a week ago; because the EU has been unable to respond to mass migration, the biggest threat to</p>
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<p>if the EU had morally comprehensive arguments and well-considered ideas regarding refugee policy. [(HUN-M31-2017). We now have the opportunity, as they conclude in Western-Europe, to cut the problem at the root and to resolve the structural issues revealed by the crises. This practically means a stronger integration in several fields, such as financial-, immigration-, foreign- and security policy. After all – as they cite the cliché – the whole European integration has resulted from crises. (HUN-M31-2017). We need it (integration) because they feel in the Member States, which Orban often points out, that: Europe is not strong enough. Neither to stay competitive on the long run, nor to adequately handle the challenges of mass migration; and nor to cope with the growing Russian influence and global instability while the security guaranteed by America seems to become weaker. (HUN-M33-2017). Though Commissioner Avramopoulos knew nothing about that, rather he was talking about a</p>	<p>they are all “nationalist” if they consider the defense of their nation and home country as their primary task, and are not willing to accept to idea of supranationalism, and do not believe that nation states are out of date. (HUN-M42-2016). “Who would deny that the biggest issue of debate in European politics is: whose Europe are we going to build? The Europe of states, the Europe of nations, perhaps the Europe of people?” – as we can read. And now we shall drop the thread of Historia (the journal article the author cites from 1996). We have to admit that the scholarly author has pointed out the nature of social restructuring and of human instincts in time, even if others – mainly sociologists of the communist and liberal tradition – have given a damn about the problem ever since. “The worse, the better” – they recited – and, indeed, it’s always been better for them.</p>	<p>troublesome, this would be doable for Hungary too. (HUN-M20-2018). And what about the cultural and civilizational price of migration, the spillover of radical Islamism, the undeniable emerge of parallel societies (thanks for the multi-culty ideology which does not require the total integration of the aliens)? (HUN-M22-2018). Each and every opposition party, even if not cheerfully, but supports Viktor Orban’s (to phrase it in a polite and moderate way) racist asylum- and fence policy. (HUN-M23-2018). The EU-Turkey deal is, of course, important to the EU, though if it is true that the fence defends us from all migratory pressure, we are not really affected by that (it is, of course, not true, but we have no leading role in this, because it is not us who pays the majority of the bill.) (HUN-M26-2018). As opposed to (?) the NER-propaganda (I would cut the first</p>	<p>Europe. Europe has been struggling with aging and shrinking population, “but this problem cannot be resolved by relying on Muslim sources and throwing our lifestyle and security out with the bathwater” - as the PM pointed out. The question is whether the leaders of Europe currently in power would finally listen to, and take his warnings and propositions seriously, which he has been repeating as ceterum censeo (sic) for nearly two years by now. (HUN-M35-2017). Rules that facilitate terrorism need to be changed – claimed the PM -, which is evidential. There is no need for a common European migration policy, but one that is tailored to nation states. Conversely, the EU keeps pushing the quota resettlement; even if things go according to the migrants’ expectation and not that of the pea-brained politicians. (HUN-M37-2017). Security has become the priority value and wish in Europe, and, beyond the leaders of the Visegrad countries, more and more responsible politicians in the EU Member States hold the same view as Orban, which he phrased</p>
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<p>consolidated approach being applied in migration matters which equally applies to our nation, and that the Western Balkan route has been stabilized, although he didn't mention, partly thanks to us.</p> <p>(HUN-M36-2017).</p> <p>When the Hungarian government defended the entire Southern Schengen border against the dangerous flux of illegal mass migration threatening Europe literally on its own – not just verbally -, when the EP - bandwagoned by the Commission – did absolutely nothing to defend the security and dignity of European citizens.</p> <p>(HUN-M36-2017).</p> <p>Nowadays, the biggest problem is that the liberal and socialist leaders of the economic and political union which calls itself European more and more distance themselves from the moral, cultural and intellectual roots of Europe. And, by placing their own power interests above all else, they do not even respect the agreements they ratified, but obstruct true Europeans and democrats. Thus, although the winter cold weather will soon be over, we shall, unfortunately</p>		<p>words, the author doesn't make sense – that's exactly what the NER says) Yes, there are no-go zones in Europe, yes, parallel Muslim societies exist, yes, mass migration creates excessive tension in European societies, yes, there are embarrassing NGOs on the Adriatic Sea. And no, the Hungarian PM is not part of the solution.</p> <p>(HUN-M27-2018).</p> <p>The governing party has dealt with migration just as much as the opposition has ignored it. There was no trace of resistance against the brutal government propaganda. Moreover, most of the time, they assisted to obscure the heart of the matter, and blur the difference between genuine refugees and the rest of the migrants.</p> <p>(HUN-M28-2018).</p> <p>If he (Sandor Nemeth) refers to migration as the primary challenge in his earlier speeches as well, then we can discuss this further, otherwise we shall consider this sentence (?), without hesitation, as the acceptance of the government's propaganda, as migration is neither among the ten, nor among the thousand most</p>	<p>in his speech in Tusvanyos six months ago as...</p> <p>(HUN-M38-2016).</p> <p>All this can still happen. As only the monkey knows exactly: red button = banana, terror = Islamist</p>
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<p>prepare ourselves, as the cold war in Europe has just started.</p> <p>(HUN-M39-2016).</p> <p>Just like the fool, harmful - both to themselves and to the public - and leftwing bureaucrats who are still in control of the top bodies of the EU. Who are not interested in stopping the illegal, economically motivated mass migration into Europe, but are plotting to spread them (migrants) in the Member States.</p> <p>HUN-M40-2016).</p> <p>Moreover, according to the Commission proposal, the directives, which leave relatively enough room to steer for Member States, would be replaced by authoritative decrees; and the migration policy (as well) would be centralized, and the decision on asylum applications would be slipped into Brussel's jurisdiction from that of Member States. And all this for what? The Commission is straightforward on that: this is all necessary because the demographic and labour market issues of Europe will be resolved by the legalization of illegal migration.</p>		<p>important issues of Europe and Hungary respectively.</p> <p>“Brussels has to be stopped” – said Viktor Orban thousands of times, because Brussels’ aim is to destroy nations and nation states, to force the flux of migrants onto Europe, and so on.</p> <p>(HUN-M30-2018).</p> <p>As it turned out, Viktor Orban – behind the people stirred up against refugees – follows precisely the migration politics of “Brussels” and “Soros”, not that he would believe in it, just as he does not believe in his own politics.</p> <p>(HUN-M43-2016).</p> <p>A vast amount of sensible European civilians agree there are lines that cannot be crossed. The European soil, the living space of European people cannot be surrendered to invaders. On the one hand, the contemporary conquest by migrants hits us hard, and we can see the globalization efforts of the powerful and the rich, on the other. Europe doesn’t wish to become the battlefield of violent missionaries and financial magnates.</p>	
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		<p>(HUN-M44-2016).</p> <p>It is hard to understand why they don't invest as much money to encourage Europeans to have children as much they invest in the education, information, employability, i.e. integration of migrants. Encouraging people to have children requires serious governmental efforts. If we are lacking it, Europe might go "extinct" by itself.</p> <p>(HUN-M45-2016).</p> <p>...and others are afraid of "them", of "the aliens". It's also understandable. How far could the situation escalate if we are split into two teams for good? Anywhere. Sweeping things under the rug, self-deception, the never-ending justification would lead to a largescale and collective suicide; the emphasis is on 'would', it would only happen if no one resisted. The later Europe starts being sensible again, and the further the leaders and opinion shapers push back the acknowledgement of danger and the admission of problems, the tougher the resistance will be.</p>	
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